

Original Article

Religious Empathy Nurtures Guidance Aptitude among Subordinates under Despotic Leadership in Higher Education

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Abstract

Purpose The purpose of this paper is to assess how educational mentors working under a despot leader tend to develop their predispositions at work and how this integration might be strengthened by despotic leadership. The present study considered its effects on male and female mentors working under a disciplinarian leader.

Design/methodology/approach

A survey was designed to collect data from teachers who teach in higher educational institutes. It is a quantitative research design, and 550 teachers were sent the inventory to fill out overall. Only 500 teachers filled it out and sent it back to the researchers. The return rate remained 81.6%.

Findings

It was identified that religious empathy plays an important role in nurturing professional aptitude when working under a despotic leader. Religious, moral values bonded the subordinates to help each other meet the standards set by the well-organized leadership. This bond seemed stronger among female teachers than male teachers who used to work individually.

Originality/value

The present research elaborated on religious empathy as a rejoinder among the workers who faced a despot leader who was working for his or her personal gains and benefits. Islamic values bound them to help their fellow beings in their time of need and their hour of defence. They showed their strength against the tyranny of despot managers by showing virtuous guidance given in the teachings of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (Peace Be upon Him).

Keywords: Religious Empathy, Moral Aptitude, Disciplined Manager, Islamic Values, Moral Ethics.

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Introduction

Religious empathy enables education leaders to understand emotions of the learners. This professional segment develops leadership faculties among teachers (Hagger, Koch, Chatzisarantis, & Orbell, 2017). Due to this faculty the educators attain acceptance and validation among their students. A teacher when acquires such culmination s/he becomes empathetic leader. Andragogical elements in a teacher seemed to prevail through the academic environment which is developed through the leadership of the educational organization (De Clercq, Haq, Raja, Azeem, & Mahmud, 2018). A voluntary leader contributes effectively to his or her coworkers' to attain mental peace during work hours enhancing their abilities to meet the challenges faced during the duty hours. On the other hand a despotic leader causes stressful environment (Taufail, Hussain, & Shahzad, 2018), obnoxious administration (Mohammad, Quoquab, Rahman, & Idris, 2015), bossy attitude, arrogance and manipulation (Islam, Ahmed, Usman, & Ali, 2021). Result of such type of leadership seemed to have a dysfunctional organizational politics and limitation in subordinates' susceptibility.

The central statement of the current research paper is to bring out effects on the performance of the educational leaders due to the despotic behavior of the organizational leadership (Din, Khan, Khan, Kadarningsih, & Astuti, 2019). The research would also suggest how religious empathy helps an individual to come out of such situations. Religious empathy devises work ethic based on honesty to work, cooperation and ethically responsible attitude. Attitude like this act as an iron wall to the despotic leaders who are mostly focusing on: self-directedness, compassionless behavior and personal manifestation. The Conservation of Resources (COR) theory (Hobfoll, Halbesleben, Neveu, & Westman, 2018) advocates that employees' work behaviour remains directly under the influence of gains and loss in such environment. This theory states further about the loss of human resources due to adverse work conditions. This theory supports gains of the workers who work under a despotic leader. This theory is quite relevant with the religious empathy which contends supportive behaviour in critical conditions prevailed due to despotic leadership in an organization. To conclude it may be assumed that the religious empathy (De Clercq & Belausteguigoitia, 2017) demands critical personal resources as a helping source to the workers performing their roles and duties under despotic boss. Especially, it holds greater impact on the female workers (Islam et al., 2021) who require more caring and nurturing environment for their duty performance.

Review of Related Literature

Authoritarian management curbs subordinates through means such as divide and rule, snubbing the voice of subordinates and overpowering their wills. This type of management usurps undesirable effects among employees (De Clercq et al., 2018). This raises diarchy and anarchy in the organization. The researches added in this portion of the related literature dealt with such studies that have already been taken and that suggested proper resolutions to this issue. The researchers suggested solutions to such issues which is variant due to its cultural, social and psychological dealings. The research done in Islamic cultural perspective tends to suggest religious empathy as a moving force to tackle this issue. The subordinates working as team can halt it spiritually. Team spiritual powers when united can act as a strong voice to stop dysfunctional ties being produced due to a tyrant. This voice would prove more powerful than the groups. This would form compassion and psychological safety to the employees who are working under a despot leader. Researches done in the past showed negative aspect development due to destructive leadership which puts a distorted impact on turnover, divergent work behaviour, passionate enervation, discontentment of worker with his or her work, and stress during work hours (Murad, Jiatong, Shahzad, & Syed, 2021). Researchers like Woestman and Wasonga [2015](#); Schyns and Schilling [2013](#); Aravena [2019](#) have already described influence of destructive behaviour on the personality and psyche of professionals which is reason of producing unmannerly management, dysfunctional leadership and unhelpful governance. A despot leader is the one who takes control of whim and vigour of the employees, makes them work like slaves and himself or herself as a governor. S/he does so just for his or her personal goals, targets and domination over the will of the employees and to topple the system (KESEN & DINCER, 2021).

Religious Empathy

Religious Empathy has both emotional and cognitive components. Empathy's emotional component is a reaction to someone else's distress that is unrelated to one's own circumstances or distress (Ziff, Ivers, & Hutton, 2017). Empathy, according to (Nesdale, de Vries Robbe, & Van Oudenhoven, 2012), involves an affective component. This suggests that empathy manifests itself as an emotional reaction to witnessing another's emotion. Empathy has cognitive aspects as well. Empathy allows a person to cognitively adopt the perspective of another person and, since they comprehend what that person is thinking, respond with similar emotions such as concern (Batson et al., 2002). It also encompasses sensitivity and concern for people who are considered to be in distress, whether close friends or strangers (Strauss et al., 2016). Self-compassion is the feeling of caring for one's own suffering (Neff & Pommier, 2013). Self-compassion has been demonstrated to be linked to perspective-taking abilities, which are linked to acts of kindness and empathy toward others. Religious empathy promotes personal and social values and helpful actions by encouraging members to be kind, sharing, forgiving, benevolent, and many other great attributes. (Bennett & Einolf, 2017). The studies approved by Lowicki, Zajenkowski, adaernelle, that religion have favorable influence on empathy. (MOHAMMADI, KAMARUDIN, & OMAR, 2020). Muslims spend their daily lives in accordance with Allah's laws, which are the source of authority in Islam and Islamic values. Allah defines rules for all Muslims in Surat al-Ma'un that are: (Mulyaningsih & Ramadani, 2017)

- Show kindness to orphans
- Support the Al-Miskin (the destitute)
- Do well for the sake of doing good rather than for the sake of a desire to impress others.
- Be helpful and polite to others.

Empathetically Nurtured aptitude among professionals

The major objective of Islamic empathy rules nurture crucial foundation for the Muslims' adherence to Islam (Gülcan, 2015). It is a system of moral guidelines, standard of behavior or values that arise when a person must choose between various options relating to moral principles (Al-Aidaros & Mohd Shamsudin, 2013). It is the pursuit of desirable values and the norms that ought to guide human aptitude and interactions. The norms that a person chooses to guide his or her capacity and the individual criteria of right and wrong (Haidt & Graham, 2007). Teachers in Pakistan working under despot leader show empathy to the students due to Islamic principles (stated above) may experience anxiety when given difficult assignments or embarrassment and frustration when they consistently fail to provide the instructor with the information they need. (Ge, Li, Chen, Kayani, & Qin, 2021). For instance, if teachers become aware of their students' fatigue before they engage in off-task activities, they may decide to adopt an alternative educational strategy (Christian-Brandt, Santacrose, & Barnett, 2020). Additionally, Educators will be able to detect how adolescents' need for independent conflicts with a rigid approach to classroom administration by viewing them from their perspective (Aldrup, Carstensen, & Klusmann, 2022).

Methodology

Sample of the Study

A study sample was selected from 500 higher education institute teachers (300 male and 200 female) and 500 teachers were taken as a sample randomly from the Universities of Pakistan. The major reason for selecting the sample from the higher educational institutes was that these institutes are infested with the despot leaders. Teachers in these institutes are given headship without prior training of human resource supervision. They are basically teachers and when they are given helms of power they found themselves torn into two pieces that is role and duty (Wramsten Wilmar, Ahlborg, Jacobsson, & Dellve, 2014). In other words, they do not know how to act as a leader and how to act as a teacher at the same time. They feel the power unbound and try to exercise it on subordinates who were once their colleagues. They become introvert and vindictive to overcome or conquer the will of their underlings. They treat them like slaves instead of treating them like their fellow helpers. This situation is currently prevailing in the educational organizations of Pakistan where

Chairperson, dean and director having power to rule their colleagues act like an authority without understanding their role and duties as facilitator. There is a dire need to provide them with human resource management training so that they may act accordingly. It was not possible to directly meet these stalwarts as they remain busy most of the time and do not find time for research even, so the researchers devised a survey for their subordinates. The survey was sent to the randomly selected teachers who are working under the despot leaders who feel to be all-knowing and self-engrossed. 60% male and 40% female teachers were sent the survey containing 15 close ended items and two open ended items. three-point Lickert scale were used to ask close ended items. SA=Strongly Agree, SDA=Strongly Disagree, N=Neutral. The complete number of filled questionnaires received from respondents was 408, which is 81.6% response rate.

Table 3.1: Detail of Sample in the study

Sr. #	No. of teachers	
01	Male	Female
02	300	200

The data was gathered using the survey method of descriptive research. The instructions for tool were made clear. Data was sent to the teachers through emails. After distribution of the survey the researchers provided assistance wherever was required to clarify the points raised by the respondents.

Data Analysis

The data collected through the questionnaire from teachers was analyzed in terms of percentage, frequency, mean, St. Deviation and regression, which is presented below:

Table 4.1: Gender of Respondents

Variables	Category	Statistics		
		f	%	S.D
Gender	Male	300	60	.49941
	Female	200	40	
Age range in years	25-35	160	29.1	.82266
	35-45	180	32.7	
	Above 45	160	38.2	
Qualification	M.Phil	200	33.6	.55170
	Ph.D	260	48.4	
	Post Doc	40	18	
Teaching Experience in years	0-5	40	7.3	.98302
	6-10	100	18.2	
	11-15	120	23.6	
	Above 15	200	50.9	

Demographic information gained from the respondents of the research was divided into gender segregation, age range qualification and teaching experience. The information tabulated in the table showed frequency of 300 male teachers from secondary school and 200 female respondents from female secondary school teaching staff. Overall, 60% male and 40% female teachers from the HEIs Participated in the survey. Reason behind less no. of female participants has been the low threshold of the respondents. The result of variable wise in mean value was 1.4000 whereas standard deviation was 0.49441. The respondents of the

research were divided into age category apartheid that the highest frequency age category 35-45 years while age group 25-35 have frequency 160 and low frequency lies at the age of category 45 above years is 160 teachers It also shows that 38.2% respondents age were above 45 years, 32.7% have 35-45 years and 29.1 % have 25-35 years. The result of variable wise in mean value was 3.0909 and standard deviation was 0.82266 values that majority of the teachers as well as sample respondents are above 45 years. The third segment taken in this regard was academic qualification. It was obvious that 33.6% of teachers have M.Phil. degree, 48.4% have Ph.D. degree and 18 percent have post-doctoral study. The result of variable wise in mean value was 2.3455 and standard deviation was 0.55170 values that majority of the teachers as well as sample respondents have done masters. The fourth variable observed teaching experience of the respondents which segregated that 18.2% of the teachers have 0-5 years' experience, 18.2% have 6-10 years' experience, 23.6% have 11-15 years' experience and 50.9% have more than 15 years' experience of teaching in the HEIs. The result of variable wise in mean value was 3.1818 and standard deviation was 0.98302 values that majority of the teachers as well as sample respondents have more than 15 years' experience.

Table 4.2 Factorial description of the statements from the Respondents

Statement	Scale	f	%	Mean	S.D
<i>My voluntaries behavior while teaching develops virtue of kindness among learners.</i>	S.A	280	56.4	1.4545	.53811
	S.D.A	210	41.8		
	N	10	1.8		
<i>Religious empathy enforces to develop the ability of truthfulness.</i>	S.A	270	56.9	1.6727	.63987
	S.D.A	230	44.1		
	N	0	0		
<i>Religious influences helps develop patience against autocratic decisions of my boss.</i>	S.A	450	92.0	1.7455	.72567
	S.D.A	40	5.0		
	N	10	3.0		
<i>I actively participate in organizational welfare activities.</i>	S.A	480	96.8	1.7455	.67270
	S.D.A	20	4.2		
	N	0	0		
<i>Religious empathy guides me to be polite in professional environment</i>	S.A	470	90.1	1.6545	.58431
	S.D.A	22	8.7		
	N	8	1.3		
<i>I believe Religious empathy is a major nurturing emphatically aptitude before despotic behavior.</i>	S.A	405	80.5	1.5273	.50386
	S.D.A	85	18.5		
	N	5	1.0		
<i>I curtail developing influences of despotism in me and transfer it to my subordinates.</i>	S.A	450	90	1.8727	.61024
	S.D.A	39	8.9		
	N	16	2.1		
<i>Religious empathy helps me to become more passionate with students.</i>	S.A	310	56.4	1.5091	.63458
	S.D.A	180	36.4		
	N	10	7.3		
<i>Religious empathy enforces me to perform my duty well.</i>	S.A	290	52.7	1.5091	.57325
	S.D.A	240	43.6		
	N	10	3.6		
<i>Religious empathy promotes forgiveness in me.</i>	S.A	210	52.7	1.5455	.63299
	S.D.A	220	40.0		
	N	70	7.3		

<i>Religious empathy develops tendencies in me to follow civic laws</i>	S.A	317	87.6	1.4345	0.51771
	S.D.A	97	11.3		
	N	46	1.1		

The information tabulated in table 4.2 showed the results of the statement asked from the respondents. The purpose of asking the first statement was to observe virtues of voluntaries behavior of teacher on learners in the class. The results indicated majority of the respondents, 56.4% strongly agreed with the statement while 41.8% teachers strongly disagreed and 1.8% teachers remained neutral about this aspect. The variable wise result identified mean value 1.4545 and standard deviation 0.53811 values that majority of the teachers as well as the sample respondents agreed with the testimonial.

Discussion

The findings of the study identified that authoritative leadership tend to show some of the dysfunctional ties which affect work ethics of the subordinates. Due to this act the organization paradigm seemed to get disturbed by impacting institutional environment, personal life, aggression increase, instability and political culture rise. All these issues give birth to favoritism, marginalization, abuse of power, blame games, injustice and hierarchical problems (Liu et al., 2019). Studies that have on them suggest that teachers with religious backgrounds and active religious convictions may be able to use their personal knowledge and experiences as a valuable teaching resource (Jackson & Everington, 2017). Strong personal convictions about a religion or religions can be a hindrance to objectivity, but the Warwick study mentioned above also demonstrates that student teachers may represent a particular religion in a way that is not objective as a result of their personal knowledge and experiences with it, and/or they may create learning opportunities that reflect those knowledge and experiences rather than taking a more comprehensive approach that takes into account the diversity within religion (Herold & Waring, 2011). One of the most important aspects of a teacher's responsibility is taking care of their students and building strong relationships with them (Aldrup et al., 2022).

Dysfunctional leaders do so by implementing differences among employees. S/he implies behaviours such as lack of integrity, taking to task the employees on their mistakes, taking credit of the hard work of employees, ridiculing them for their tasks, using abusive language, yelling and accusing them loudly to subvert their self-respect. Such harmful acts are imposed upon them so that they may not be able to work whole heartedly, without lead of despot and seeking permission for each and every act within the organization (Stuppy & Mead, 2017).

High-quality classrooms also offer high levels of emotional support, which can be seen in the classroom's positive emotional tone, responses to students' intellectual, social, and emotional requirements as well as; awareness of their interests (Jerome, Hamre, & Pianta, 2009). Empathy, or the capacity to understand students' nonverbal signals, is essential for achieving this (Jerome et al., 2009). For instance, a teacher's cognitive empathy will enable them to more accurately read a student's facial expressions to determine whether they are depressed over a poor grade, irate over a disagreement with friends, or bored with a particular learning activity.

Teachers with empathy understand that students may experience anxiety when given difficult assignments or embarrassment and frustration when they consistently fail to provide the instructor with the information they need. (Ge et al., 2021). These concepts are incorporated into the social classroom paradigm (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009), which also asserts that educators social and emotional competency, of which empathy is a part, that should male easier classroom management In order to maintain order in the classroom, teachers must set rules, use proper discipline techniques, and maximize student focus (Agbaria, 2021). Understanding the causes of disturbances in the classroom may help with behavior control.

For instance, if teachers become aware of their students' fatigue before they engage in off-task activities, they may decide to adopt an alternative educational strategy (Christian-Brandt et al., 2020). Additionally, Educators will be able to detect how adolescents' need for independent conflicts with a rigid approach to classroom administration by viewing them from their perspective (Aldrup et al., 2022). Although

emotional support from teachers may be more important for good classroom management. After all, classroom management involves a number of aspects beyond empathy, like the creation of norms and the efficient use of time.

Knowledge of certain classroom management techniques is a crucial requirement for these responsibilities (Kunter et al., 2013). The third crucial element of excellent teacher-student connection is instructional support, which teacher empathy may help with additional providing of emotional assistance and classroom administration. However, this is not emphasized in the prosocial classroom model. Clear and interesting education that encourages material understanding and presents cognitive problems makes up instructional support. Additionally, teachers scaffold learning by giving comments and leading class discussions about the course material (Aldrup et al., 2022).

There are a variety of tests that can be used to assess empathy, each having its own set of sample variants. Because our existence is dependent on other individuals' people, groups, communities, societies, the world, and even the universe, as we are a part of it (Ilgunaite, Giromini, & Di Girolamo, 2017). We should try to comprehend our own feelings. During a medical interview, empathy is a powerful and efficient communication tool. Empathy goes beyond the patient's history and symptoms to incorporate the patient's values, thoughts, and feelings. Both the physician and the patient benefit from more sympathetic communication. Rumi's poetry, particularly the author's first two books *Masnawai*, promotes self-awareness and empathy at the core of humanity. His Sufis teachings are without a doubt acquiring global recognition, transcending geographical and ethnic barriers (Nafisah, 2022).

Research Findings from Respondents

Findings are presented that are retrieved from data collected through questionnaires. The findings from the data set were based on the results derived from concerning sampled diffident. It was found that the despotic behavior of the manager/leader affects such virtue growth among the subordinates as: kindness, volunteer habits, sharing and caring, communicative competence, telling a lie, emotive to work on their own, personal opinion making, get guidance at the time of need. They were of the view that this effect brought drastic change in their personality and psyche in the beginning. They found themselves all engrossed in themselves. They felt their freedom was captured due to unethical behavior of the leaders. The single force of religion acted as a guide and nurtured them with the ability to develop their personality. This source rescued their approach towards religious empathy which taught them to believe in themselves and never to be the slaves of anyone in this world. The scriptures taught them that they were born free and there is only one, The Allah, Almighty whom they bent five times a day and their belief in the Day of Judgment made them perform their duties freely and for the will of Allah. This worked upon them, and they acted frequently, calmly, patiently, with tolerance, forbearance and vigorously.

They identified that it was religious empathy that enforced the ability of truthfulness, developed patience, development of moral values, social welfare, ethics, empathy, professionalism, politeness in affairs, ethical behavior enhancement, kindness with subordinates, lead the fellow who are down trodden and to develop brotherhood at the hour of need among them. Negative criticism is one of the key weapons among despots which breeds disparity in the minds. This element distorts creative ability, and all the time individuals keep on thinking or evaluating his or her personal abilities. This causes brawls among professionals, and they get themselves divided into parties. In other words, polarization gets started among individuals. This division helps the despot boss to divide and rule the subordinate under him or her. This kind of politics and party division is poisonous for the organizational structure if it gets worse. The respondents identified that they were divided into organizational politics before they started thinking about religious empathy which helped them to think that there is only one Allah who is the creator and sustainer. Due to His will all blessings are imparted upon men. He is the one who gives respect and who takes respect. He gives wages to all, and He knows whom to exalt and whom to befall. This philosophy helped them to overcome the professional jealousy among them.

Religious empathy leads them towards act of compassion as majority of the teachers agreed that religion is a binding force among human beings. Personal respect is the one which can be earned through giving respect to other human beings. One cannot earn respect until or unless one delivers respect to others.

A person who is emotionally well settled holds calm and peace in oneself. There is positive reinforcement instead of all-time criticism in professional ethics. If a person is praised all time s/he will infatuate and develop such qualities within days about which s/he is being boosted for. Especially among teachers who are critical thinkers and who are to develop a nation they require passion and self-respect. It was found that the teachers required having ego so that they might be able to stand with dignity before their students. In such case only religious empathy helped them to become more passionate, to understand misery of others which is reflected in their conduct, character and personality predominantly.

It was found that this positive enforcement helps them to perform their professional duties in a better way. It happened to promote forgiveness in the observers and religious empathy imparted in them tendencies to follow civic laws. Due to this observance the teachers at higher level working under a despotic leader develop patience kind behavior, fair dealings in the life and acknowledgment of leader's point of view to promote peace in organization. This helps them to develop due professionalism in them. Religious philosophy nurtures and acts as a guide to come out of the problematic social situation where a person finds him or herself. Islamic principles are guidelines for the observers to enhance ethical behavior, attainment of purity and discipline in life. Religious belief plays key role in making friendly relations with others which leads to act of compassion inclination to feel anxious when my fellows feel anxiety they pay close attention to the emotional states of their fellows in institute. Religious empathy influences them towards development of moral values, ethical behavior and virtuosity.

Conclusions

It may be concluded on the basis of the data retrieved from the respondents who participated in the survey designed by the researchers. Religious education develops tendencies among higher education institute leaders to follow civic laws. Their kind behavior while teaching develops virtue of kindness among them. They become fair in their life dealing that helps them to mark up this virtue in their ethics. Majority of teachers agreed that they acknowledged learners' point of view to promote peace in society. Religious empathy enforces to develop the ability of truthfulness. It also helps to develop patience among teachers. Religion influences teachers' aptitude and develops moral values. Teachers actively participate in the welfare activities. Religious empathy influences teachers to be polite with learners. Religious empathy is a source of enhancing ethical behavior. This enhancement among teachers makes them tender and kind in their dealings. Their dialogue with a despot leader can infer the emotional conditions of the leader. They typically have empathy for such managers who remain unhappiness and feelings. Religious empathy helps me to become more passionate with students and understand other misery. It may be concluded that religious empathy enhances their conduct that leads to ethical behavior and enforces them to perform their duty well. Religious empathy promotes forgiveness and understands kindness and its values among students.

From the result it was concluded that religious empathy imparted from their teacher develops tendencies in students to follow civic laws. Religious empathy displayed in an organization helps them to develop patience. According to study it is noted that teachers' kind behavior develops virtue of kindness in secondary school learners. Fairness of dealing helps them to mark up this virtue. Religion is strong boost to develop habit of truthfulness driven from emphatically behavior. This nurtures welfare activities of subordinates' influence to participate in social welfare activities. Due to professional behavior of teachers, they become passionate about their daily routines. Purity and discipline are diminished under a despot leader but in this issue, religious belief plays key role in making friendly relation with others. Religious empathy may lead to acts of compassion. When their fellows are upset and sad due to despotic behaviors of their leader, they are also very sad and when their fellows feel anxious, they are also feeling anxious. They infer their fellows' emotional feelings from their communication to pick their low spirits to high morals.

Power Analysis

The findings from the present study provided helpful indications and suggestions about Religious Empathy Nurtures Guidance Aptitude among Subordinates of a Despotic Leadership in the Higher Educational Institutes.

It is recommended that University administrators conduct properly followed training on politeness policy. Human Resource Management should pay attention to traditional leadership need to be changed into friendly environments where teachers constantly value academic growth and development of moral values. This research study helps to fill the knowledge gaps existing in the field of education and higher educational institutes. It contributes to the issues regarding the educational professionals who work under the tyrannous grip of their bosses who were once the colleagues. This research describes true picture of such educationists who are still waiting for better times to prevail in the system but there is no such solution existed till date. The Chairpersons and Deans of the departments and faculties are giving them tough time. Their duty demands peace and harmony. Their bosses, instead of developing such conducive environment continue to stress them all the time with extra work, duties and functions which are not related to their role. This makes them aggressive and away from their job of delivery, that is teaching the youth. They are instead engrossed in the way to jealousy, prejudice and negative feelings. This can be decreased only and only by the intervention of the higher authorities such as HEC and Vice Chancellor and the Chancellor. There should be two cadres to tackle the situation. The academic in charge should be different from the managerial in charge. If a professor is promoted as a head, it means loss of a good teacher at the time when s/he is at a verge to deliver knowledge and impart his or her experiences.

Contribution

The present research contributes to the extent how religious empathy acts as a catalyst to maintain balance in an organization working under a despot leader who just works for his or her personal interest and gains. S/he exploits educational leaders and puts a negative effect on the behaviour of volunteer workers. This type of leader is considered to be human resource drainer as s/he demotivates them which impact the voluntary efforts of the workers under him or her. Due to this demotivation professionalism and empathy towards students is affected. This type of leadership especially impact on female who feel harassed and diffused. Social aspect of the workers diminishes and distorts them making them feel less like robots. Creativity and skill transfer stops and only criticism and ironic situations prevail which is despotic to the minds. Female workers who are more helping than male workers seemed to be affected due to the triggering role of despotic leadership. This leadership style can be tackled through religious work values which encourages helping behaviour among workers. The present study unequivocally discourses this type of intervention.

This study is novel in its context as it investigates the effect of despotic leaders on the aptitude of the teachers teaching at the higher level. The context taken in this research is Pakistani where there is Islamic work ethics (IWE) being observed. Major context of the study was relevant to the gender, despotic leaders and religious empathy. Since religion (Islam) is main focus of the employees working in Pakistan (Kakar & Khan, 2021). Researches already taken in this context showed that there are variations in Muslim countries too stating dark sides of the leadership incipient in these countries (Raja, Haq, De Clercq, & Azeem, 2020) & (Usman et al., 2020). So, the major context of the present study is about collective role of an Islamic work ethic, authoritarian leadership, and gender among Pakistani employees. Religion plays an important role in aptitude development of the workers and clients. Basic teachings of a religion coincide with all the religions of the world that are empathy, ethics and social development of human beings (Ali et al., 2022)

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